

Recommended citation: Ehnberg, J. (2021). Cost effective on-line master thesis fair. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 819-827). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14650280.

COST EFFECTIVE ON-LINE MASTER THESIS FAIR

J. Ehnberg¹

Department of Electrical Engineering
Chalmers University of Technology
Göteborg

Conference Key Areas: *Digital tools, Changes beyond Covid -19*

Keywords: *Virtual fair, Professional network, Master thesis, Corona, Industry relations*

ABSTRACT

Under corona restrictions it was expected to be extra hard to find an opportunity to do a master thesis in cooperation with a company as is the praxis in the investigated context. To mitigate this, a special master thesis fair was held in the area of Electric power engineering as most normally arranged fairs and other opportunities for the students to meet companies had been cancelled.

For economic and practical reasons was Zoom and the function on break-out room used. A two-hour event was held with 15 companies, consisting of a mix of local, national, and international companies. The companies were given a great freedom to act within their respective break-out room. Around three quarters of the second-year students, in a two-year program, attended as well as a few from the first year. Initially the students, especially the international, focused on the big and international companies, like Ericsson, ABB and Volvo Cars, but then they were also looking for opportunities at smaller local companies. This created some waiting times, both for the students and some of the small and less known companies.

Both the students and most of the companies were satisfied and it was clear that all wanted the arrangement to be repeated, some even if there would be no pandemic. The fair fulfilled its purpose but also gave insights on how future fairs, with limited economical resources, could be arranged, The recommendations are presented in form of a list at the end.

¹ Corresponding author:

J. Ehnberg

jimmy.ehnberg@chalmers.se

1 INTRODUCTION

In year 2020, suddenly everything was different due to the Corona pandemic. Physical meetings in large gatherings were not allowed, but life had to continue anyway somehow. Most teaching at Chalmers were converted into distant teaching to prevent Corona spread. Cooperation with industry was also limited and turned into distant guest lectures or virtual study visits with very small possibilities to allow students and industry representatives to meet individually or in small groups.

In [1]–[5] it is stated that there are many benefits of cooperation between industry and academia in engineering education. Apart from the benefits in technical areas [1], it may also increase the sense of identity as future engineer [2] for the students as well as an improved self-efficacy for their future professional development both in lifelong learning and professional success [3]. In [4] was the idea presented that students' development of multidisciplinary skills may benefit through such cooperation. Also, companies may favour cooperation since working together on a thesis is a way to test a potential employee and to get questions answered that are not important enough to be funded internally. It might also create a connection to the university to get new ideas or knowledge, often more theoretical [3], [5]. In [4] digital tools are seen as a good way to increase cooperation since it gives a access to world class expertise at a low cost.

Improving their professional network is extra important for students that are close to graduation. Different types of fairs are well suited for expanding professional networks [6]. Normally, there are several career fairs arranged at Chalmers with different focuses, among others one in Electric power engineering, but not in 2020.

The transition into distant teaching required a great work effort for most of the teachers and therefore fairs needed to be arranged with minimal resources. Physical fairs will probably also play an important role also in the future but on-line fairs will be needed as a complement to increase accessibility, e.g. geographical [7] which is highly relevant for Swedish conditions. However, in [8] is it argued that virtual fairs, will become the preferred option in the future due to the possibilities for visibility and branding, costs and it is easier to evaluate due to access to metadata of the fair. However, there are several aspects that need to be considered when organising a fair with high student satisfaction. The identified success factors are apart from the organisation itself also exhibitor performance and pre-event services [9].

Doing a master thesis in cooperation with a company is one of the first ways for a student to utilize their professional network. It is a popular way for the students to both expand their professional network but also to get the first job [10]. It is for many students their first real occasion where they could put their newly gained theoretical knowledge to some practical use. It also give some experience on how it is to work as an engineer. At the investigated educational programme around 80 % of the students each year make their master project in close cooperation with industry.

The purpose of this study is to investigate if it is suitable to organize a master thesis fair in Zoom and to establish recommendation for future master thesis fairs under similar circumstance or to utilize the identified benefits. The target groups of this paper are teachers and administrators that need to create opportunities for students and their professional networking and are considering using a digital tool but have limited resources.

2 THE FAIR

The fair was organised on the 30th of September 2020 and had a clear focus on master thesis cooperation within the area of Electric power engineering. The date was approximately three and a half months before the students are expected to start their thesis work. The fair was 2 hours long and organised by Chalmers. Only students from the master's program in Electric power engineering were invited as a way to limit the number of participating students since it was the number of students that was predicted to be the bottleneck in the flow during the fair.

The master's program in Electric power engineering at Chalmers is an international two-year program and currently has approximately 50 students per year, where around 20 have a bachelor's degree from Chalmers.

Approximately 35 second year students and 5 first year students participated in the fair. International, national and local companies were invited to attend and 15 signed up, for example ABB, Volvo and Ericsson but also more local ones like Gothenburg Energy. The participating companies represented the categories; power utilities, design of electric drive systems, power components manufacturers, and consultancy firms.

To keep the cost low Zoom was used. The organiser arranged a meeting and then assigned each company a so-called breakout-room. This meant that the organiser had to direct each participant personally to the breakout-room of their choice. The number of participants in each breakout-room was limited to 10 persons.

3 EVALUATION METHOD

Two questionnaires were sent out, one to the students and one to the companies. The questionnaire for students started with question on how many companies they attended while the first question in the company questionnaire was regarding number of students that visited them. The last three questions were the same;

- How valuable were these visits for you?
- How well do think it was arranged?
- Do you think we should arrange this kind of fair next year?

The answers were all multiple choice and the options can be seen in Figure 1 to Figure 5. In addition, there were opportunities to send free text answers via mail to the organiser. Only 3 companies used this possibility. Observations were also done by the organiser.

As a follow up were the cooperation rate during the pandemic investigated and compared to the rate before. This was done by an investigation of whatever thesis works that were initiated were done in cooperation with a company or not. The students of the non-company related thesis works were approach individually for some follow up questions.

IV. OUTCOME

Approximately 60 % of the participating students answered the questionnaire and the number of companies each student meet can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Number of companies each student meet during the two-hour fair.

In Figure 1, it can be seen that most students visited more than one company which indicates that the students were not focused on one meeting only.

Just above 85 % of the companies answered the questionnaire. Figure 2 shows the number of students that meet each company.

Figure 2. Number students that visited each company during the two-hour fair.

Some companies were more popular than others. It was mainly the large international companies while companies with less known brands were not that interesting in the beginning. One company did not get any visitor the first hour and then left the meeting. However, some students asked for the company after they had left.

In Figure 3 is the considered value of the fair shown.

Figure 3 shows how valuable the students and the companies thought the fair was.

Figure 3 shows how valuable the fair was considered to be by the students and the companies. The students thought the fair were more valuable than the companies did. The one answer 'useless' is likely explained by the fact that one company left before they had received any students in their room.

The third question was on how well the fair was organised and the answers of the students and companies can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. How well the students and the companies though it was organized.

The answers on organisation were more spread than the answers of the other questions. The situation for the organiser directing students was occasionally chaotic but after adapting a more direct approach for directing of the students, it went much smoother. The last question was whether the students and the companies wanted the fair to return next year and answers can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Answers on if the students and company representatives would like the event to return and if that case how.

All agreed that the fair should be repeated but how was more dispersed, as the students preferred a physical one while the companies were more eager to see another digital one.

Also 2021 around 80 % started their thesis work in cooperation with a company. However, most of the other students, that didn't cooperate with a company, said that they tried to find a company but had a too specific project idea to find a suitable partner. Only one state that he could not find any possibility to cooperate with a company.

4 DISCUSSION

In general, the students were more positive to the fair than the companies. This may be explained by the fact that discussing master thesis seems to be more urgent for an individual student than a company. The fair was probably extra valuable for the international students as their professional network in Sweden might be more limited than for the students with a domestic background.

The organisation seemed to be the weak link of the fair. The facts that the organiser had to personally direct all students to the different breakout rooms which created some frustration. However after the fair, an option for the students to join break-out rooms themselves was added to Zoom. Some companies had problems handling the constant dropping in and out of students, because they wanted more control the flow of the information which was probably due to changed the power balance in the meetings.

No student visited more than 7 companies probably because there was not time to meet all. Longer time would have been better for the less known companies since many students were not interested until they had ensured that they had meet the large ones.

A single zoom meeting with breakout-rooms had its clear advantages since the organiser was in the main room could both control the flow of the students and guide students to companies they might know less well. However, for a more general fair it

would be harder since no long discussions were possible, the students needed to be well prepared and organiser well aware of both the situation of the students and the companies if it should work.

Companies were more positive to a digital conference also next year than the students. The reasons behind this could be less time required for participation and less travel cost [7], [8]. Despite the facts the students are a part of the younger generation, they were more positive to meet face to face. This is an interesting view and worth looking into deeper but it could a consequence of all the other aspects related well-being of students during the COVID-19 pandemic as discussed in [11]. Therefore, the such a reevaluation should be done without the threat of an pandemic before conclusive statements are done.

5 CONCLUSIONS

It is possible to organise a master thesis fair at zoom, at least in 2020, if the number of participants is limited to around 50. It is expected to be appropriate as a complement to a physical event even without corona restrictions. The on-line approach seemed to be especially appealing to the companies.

6 RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations for arranging master thesis fairs can be made based on this work:

- On-line fairs are suitable for fair on topics with high level of specialisation.
- Keep the guiding resource in the meeting but if it is a highly specified fair the guide must be well familiar with the field.
- Make a test run with the company representatives.
- Advise the companies on which structure to use, so it fits the arrangement.
- Pre-event information about the different companies is needed to guide the students more, at least towards the less known companies.
- The event must be long enough so that there are opportunities for the students to visit all the companies they want to visit.
- Insert a break in the fair to allow students to communicate with each other to spread the word about less known companies or cool ideas.

7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge all the students and the company representatives that contributed into making this fair such a success.

REFERENCES

- [1] Valdez, M. T., Ferreira, C. M. and Barbosa, F. P. M. (2019), Enhancing Electric Energy Systems Final Project through Real Engineering Design Problems, *Proc. of 2019 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)*, Dubai, pp. 823–826.
- [2] Mann, L., Howard, P., Nouwens, F. and Martin F., (2009) Influences on the Development of Students' Professional Identity as an Engineer, *Research in Engineering Education Symposium*, pp. 1–6.
- [3] Anders A. D., (2018), Networked learning with professionals boosts students' self-efficacy for social networking and professional development, *Comput. Educ.*, vol. 127, pp. 13–29.
- [4] Kazmierkowski, M. P., Piasecki, S., Blaabjerg, F., Chiu, H.-J. and Jasinski, M. (2020), Fruitful Cooperation Between Science and Industry Is Possible: We Prove By Examples [Students and Young Professionals News], *IEEE Ind. Electron. Mag.*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 102–110.
- [5] Moro, P. C., Neves, P. F., de Carvalho, A. C. K., Vetroni, B. M. and Rodrigo, S. (2019), LCA and ecodesign teaching via university-industry cooperation, *Int. J. Sustain. High. Educ.*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 1061–1079.
- [6] Kaskey, V., (2012) An Investigation into a Career Day on a Student's Choice of Profession, *Int. J. Bus. Soc. Sci.*, vol. 3, no. 14, pp. 53–58.
- [7] McIlveen, P., Hoare P. N., McKeown, L. and Vagg, K. (2009) Internet Career Fairs in Australian Higher Education, Toowoomba 4350.
- [8] Vik, Å. S. Nørbech, B. C. and Jeske, D. (2018), Virtual Career Fairs: Perspectives from Norwegian Recruiters and Exhibitors, *Future Internet* , vol. 10, no. 2.
- [9] Lee, M. J., Lee, P. C. Dopson, L. R. and Yoon, S. (2020), What dimensions of career expos have the most impact on student satisfaction?, *J. Hosp. Leis. Sport Tour. Educ.*, vol. 27, p. 100263
- [10] Lopes, F. Fonseca, I. and Ferreira C. (2018), An Industry-Oriented Master's Degree in Electrical Engineering - Automation and Communications in Energy and Industrial Systems - Operation and Industry Cooperation Review," *Proc. of 2018 28th EAEEIE Annual Conference (EAEEIE)*, Reykjavik, pp. 1–9.
- [11] Yilmazli Trout I. and Alsandor, D. J. (2021) Graduate student well-being: Learning and living in the U.S. during the COVID-19 pandemic, *Int. J. Multidiscip. Perspect. High. Educ.*, vol. 5, no. 1 SE-Pandemic Essays, pp. 150–155.